

PREREGISTRATION

Cognitive Inoculation Against FIMI Susceptibility

A Randomised Controlled Trial on a French Adult Population

Version 2 — 27 May 2026

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Preregistration DOI	10.5281/zenodo.20403018
Related working paper	10.5281/zenodo.20353828
Experimental platform	inoculation.fr
Academic site	epistemique.fr
Status at deposit	<i>Confirmatory data collection on the representative French adult population has not yet begun at the time of deposit. A prior technical validation phase has been conducted on a non-representative convenience sample (see Section 1.2). The present preregistration governs the confirmatory phase initiated after this deposit.</i>
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1. Background and rationale

Foreign Information Manipulation and Interference (FIMI) operations targeting France and the European Union have intensified since 2022. The European External Action Service has documented a systematic increase in their scale, sophistication, and political impact. Counter-disinformation measures based on post-hoc correction (fact-checking, debunking, platform sanctions) face well-established structural limitations: the delay between exposure and correction, the asymmetric reach of false content versus its rectification, and the entrenchment of belief through repeated exposure.

Inoculation theory, developed by McGuire (1961) and substantially extended over the past decade by van der Linden, Roozenbeek and colleagues, provides an alternative paradigm. By exposing participants to weakened forms of manipulation techniques before they encounter the genuine article, inoculation interventions aim to confer cognitive resistance prior to exposure. Meta-analytic evidence (Banas and Rains, 2010; Compton et al., 2020) supports the general efficacy of the approach, though effect sizes vary substantially by population, manipulation type, and intervention modality.

The present trial evaluates a brief, text-based inoculation intervention specifically designed against the manipulation techniques documented in the empirical corpus of FIMI operations targeting France between 2019 and 2025. Five operational stimuli are administered: two derived from the Doppelganger/RRN operation (domain spoofing of Le Monde and Ouest-France), two derived from the Matryoshka operation (Twitter/X impersonation of a real journalist; Facebook astroturfing post), and one derived from the Storm-1516 operation (deepfake audio attributed to a spoofed news outlet). Two authentic control stimuli are interleaved to permit signal-discrimination analysis.

1.1 Relation to the doctoral thesis

The trial constitutes Strand B of a four-strand convergent mixed-methods doctoral research programme conducted within the framework of an Executive PhD at the Centre d'Études Diplomatiques et Stratégiques (CEDS, Paris), under the supervision of Prof. Michael Strauss. The other strands comprise: (A) a systematic forensic analysis of documented FIMI operations targeting France between 2019 and 2025; (C) an expert consultation programme with French parliamentarians, regulators, and senior practitioners; (D) a comparative composite index (Epistemic Security Score) applied to five European Union member states. The trial's primary contribution to the thesis is to test, in a French general-population sample, whether a cognitive inoculation intervention reduces susceptibility to manipulation techniques observed in real FIMI operations targeting France.

1.2 Pre-deposit technical validation phase

Prior to the present deposit, a technical validation phase was conducted on the experimental platform inoculation.fr. This phase ran with a convenience sample of 26 close associates of the principal investigator, all holding postgraduate qualifications (Bac+5 or above) and several professionally familiar with information manipulation topics. The purpose of this phase was strictly operational: to verify the technical integrity of the experimental pipeline (consent flow, randomisation logic, stimulus presentation, response capture, demographics module, completion funnel, database integrity, and CSV export). It

was not designed, conducted, or analysed as a pilot study of the efficacy of the inoculation intervention.

Three properties of this convenience sample make any inferential interpretation of its outputs methodologically unsound, and the principal investigator preemptively declares them here for full transparency. First, the sample is non-representative of the French adult population on every relevant dimension: educational attainment is uniformly at the post-graduate level (Bac+5+), professional networks are skewed toward sectors with above-average familiarity with information manipulation, and recruitment was through personal acquaintance with the investigator rather than through quota sampling. Second, baseline resistance to FIMI in such a sample is expected to be substantially higher than in a representative population, creating ceiling effects on the primary outcome. Third, the small size ($n = 26$ at the close of this phase) provides no usable statistical power for inferential testing of the preregistered hypotheses.

No inferential analysis of this phase is conducted, no effect-size or significance claim is or will be drawn from it, and no information from this phase is used to formulate, modify, or restrict the hypotheses or analysis plan preregistered below. The hypotheses below derive from prior theory and prior meta-analytic evidence (Compton et al., 2020; Roozenbeek and van der Linden, 2024). The confirmatory phase, governed exclusively by this preregistration, is initiated after the deposit date and recruits a representative French adult sample through the procedures described in Section 4.

1.3 Continuous research model

This research is conducted as continuous open science. The present preregistration governs the analysis plan for all data collected under the confirmatory phase regardless of when those data are extracted for reporting. Three types of release are anticipated, none of which alter the present preregistration.

- **Doctoral manuscript reporting (Q2-Q3 2026):** descriptive and, conditional on the sample-size threshold defined in Section 6.6, inferential results based on the data collected up to the date of manuscript submission. The achieved sample size at that date will be reported transparently.
- **Interim Zenodo releases:** periodic dataset releases on Zenodo as a versioned series linked to this preregistration, providing the research community with the anonymised dataset at fixed temporal milestones, accompanied by descriptive statistics only.
- **Final results report:** once the target sample size defined in Section 4.4 is reached, a results report is deposited on Zenodo as a separate document citing this preregistration, with the full pre-specified analyses applied to the complete confirmatory dataset.

The preregistration is the fixed reference point. The data, the dashboard at inoculation.fr, and the published reports evolve as the collection proceeds.

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2. Hypotheses

Three confirmatory hypotheses are preregistered. They are stated in their substantive form and operationalised in Sections 5 and 6.

H1 — Primary effect (credibility)

Participants in the inoculation condition will rate FIMI stimuli as less credible than participants in the control condition. Operationally, this is tested as a between-conditions difference on the participant-level mean credibility rating across the five FIMI stimuli, with the inoculated mean lower than the control mean.

H2 — Secondary effect (sharing intent)

Participants in the inoculation condition will report a lower intention to share FIMI stimuli than participants in the control condition. Operationally, between-conditions difference on the participant-level mean sharing-intent rating across the five FIMI stimuli, with the inoculated mean lower than the control mean.

H3 — Specificity (control stimuli)

The inoculation effect does not generalise to authentic content. There is no substantively meaningful between-conditions difference in credibility ratings of the two authentic control stimuli. This is a directional hypothesis of no difference, evaluated through an equivalence procedure (Section 6.5).

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3. Design

Type	Two-arm parallel-group randomised controlled trial.
Allocation	1:1 simple randomisation, server-side, at the participant level, upon entry to the platform after consent.
Conditions	Inoculation arm receives a brief text-based pre-exposure inoculation module. Control arm receives a length-matched neutral text on an unrelated civic topic. Stimuli presentation is identical between arms.
Blinding	Participants are blind to condition assignment and to

	the existence of a second condition. Analyses are conducted on de-identified data with condition labels masked until the analysis script is finalised and locked.
Stimuli	Seven stimuli per participant: five FIMI (s1 Doppelganger Le Monde; s2 Doppelganger Ouest-France; s3 Matryoshka Twitter/X; s4 Matryoshka Facebook; s5 Storm-1516 deepfake audio) and two authentic controls (s6 Le Monde; s7 Ministère de la Culture). Order is randomised between participants.
Setting	Online, asynchronous, self-administered by participants on the platform inoculation.fr.
Phase separation	The platform records a phase flag at the session level (technical_validation vs. confirmatory). Only sessions flagged confirmatory enter the analyses defined in Section 6.

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4. Participants (confirmatory phase)

4.1 Eligibility

- Adults aged 18 or over.
- Residence in metropolitan France.
- Sufficient French-language reading proficiency to complete the procedure without assistance (self-assessed at consent).
- Informed consent provided at platform entry.

4.2 Exclusions

- Participants who withdraw consent at any point.
- Participants identified as duplicate enrolments by IP address, account identifier, or cookie-level deduplication.
- Participants whose completion time falls in the lowest 2.5 percent of the distribution at the analysis cut-off (speeders).
- Sessions flagged technical_validation in the platform database (the 26 pre-deposit convenience-sample sessions described in Section 1.2).

4.3 Recruitment

Confirmatory-phase participants are recruited through a combination of channels: (a) direct visits to inoculation.fr, (b) social media and professional network promotion, (c) email outreach to professional networks and educational institutions, and (d) a paid recruitment supplement on a quota-sample online

panel provider, calibrated to INSEE adult-population distributions on age, gender, and region. The relative contribution of each channel is recorded for sensitivity analysis but is not used to determine inclusion.

4.4 Target sample size

The target sample size for the confirmatory phase is $n = 200$ per condition (total $n = 400$ completers passing data-quality checks). This target is calibrated to detect a between-conditions standardised mean difference of $d = 0.30$ with statistical power of 0.80 at a two-sided significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, an effect size consistent with the conservative end of the prior meta-analytic literature (Compton et al., 2020).

Minimum reportable threshold for confirmatory inference: $n = 100$ per condition. Should the achieved sample fall below this threshold at the date of any given report (doctoral manuscript submission or intermediate Zenodo release), only descriptive statistics are reported and inferential analysis is deferred to a later report.

The target can be revised upward through versioned amendment to this preregistration, but cannot be revised downward.

4.5 Compensation and ethics

Participation is voluntary and unpaid. The platform provides participants with a debrief at completion explaining the purpose of the trial, the nature of the manipulation techniques observed in real FIMI operations, and contact information for the research team. Participants may withdraw their data at any point through a withdrawal link associated with their unique participant identifier. The procedure is consistent with the ethical standards of the CEDS doctoral programme and with the Declaration of Helsinki principles applicable to minimal-risk online research.

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5. Measures

5.1 Primary outcome

Credibility rating per stimulus, on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = not credible at all, 7 = entirely credible). The primary endpoint is the participant-level mean credibility rating across the five FIMI stimuli (s1 to s5).

5.2 Secondary outcomes

- Sharing intent per stimulus, captured on a three-level scale (No / Maybe / Yes) per item. Participant-level summary across the five FIMI stimuli.

- Credibility rating per authentic control stimulus (s6, s7), used to test specificity (H3).
- Signal-discrimination score: percentage of the seven stimuli correctly assessed (FIMI rated as low credibility, authentic rated as high credibility) per participant.
- Manipulation check on the inoculation message: two comprehension items per inoculated participant, with pass criterion preregistered as endorsement of the correct alternative on both items.

5.3 Covariates collected for descriptive and moderator analysis

- Age (continuous, with categorical recoding for cohort analyses).
- Gender (categorical, with INSEE-consistent options).
- Region (categorical, INSEE-consistent).
- Highest completed level of education (ordinal).
- Self-reported political orientation (seven-point left-right scale, with a "prefer not to answer" option).
- Self-reported attention to the procedure (seven-point scale).
- Recruitment channel (categorical, captured server-side).

5.4 Process indicators

- Time spent on each stimulus (seconds).
- Total session duration.
- Order of stimulus presentation.
- Phase flag (technical_validation vs. confirmatory).

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6. Analysis plan (confirmatory phase only)

All analyses below apply exclusively to sessions flagged confirmatory in the platform database. Sessions flagged technical_validation are excluded from every analysis in this section.

6.1 Confirmatory analysis (H1)

A Welch two-sample t-test on the participant-level mean credibility rating across FIMI stimuli, comparing the inoculated condition to the control condition. Two-sided. Alpha = 0.05. Effect size reported as Cohen's d with 95 percent confidence interval. Sensitivity analysis: non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test in the event of marked non-normality, defined as Shapiro-Wilk $p < 0.001$ in either condition.

6.2 Confirmatory analysis (H2)

Chi-square test of independence on the three-level sharing-intent distribution (No / Maybe / Yes) by condition, aggregated across the five FIMI stimuli at the participant level. Effect size reported as Cramér's V. Alpha = 0.05.

6.3 Confirmatory analysis (H3, specificity)

Two One-Sided Tests (TOST) equivalence procedure on the credibility rating of authentic control stimuli (s6, s7), comparing conditions. Equivalence bounds: $d = -0.20$ to $d = +0.20$. Alpha = 0.05 per side.

6.4 Moderator analyses (exploratory)

The following moderators are preregistered as exploratory:

- Age cohort (18-34 / 35-54 / 55+), tested through condition-by-cohort interaction in a linear model on the primary outcome.
- Manipulation-check pass status, tested through restriction of the confirmatory analysis to manipulation-check passers (per-protocol sensitivity analysis).
- Education level (Bac and below / Bac+2 to Bac+3 / Bac+4 and above), tested through condition-by-education interaction.
- Recruitment channel (panel vs. organic), tested through condition-by-channel interaction.

Moderator analyses are flagged as exploratory and are not used to modify the confirmatory conclusions.

6.5 Missing data and inclusion

Confirmatory analysis is conducted on the modified intention-to-treat sample: all randomised confirmatory-phase participants who provided complete responses on the five FIMI stimuli, regardless of manipulation-check status. Participants who completed the procedure but had partial item-level missingness on one or more FIMI stimuli are included with their available ratings, the participant-level mean being computed over observed items.

A per-protocol sensitivity analysis (Section 6.4) restricts the sample to manipulation-check passers in the inoculated condition.

6.6 Inferential safeguards

- **Pre-specified sample size threshold for inference:** no inferential test is reported below $n = 100$ per condition. Below this threshold, only descriptive statistics are reported.
- **Pre-specified analyses only:** any analysis not listed in Section 6 is reported as exploratory, with no inferential claim attached.

- **No optional stopping:** inferential analysis is conducted at a fixed analysis cut-off per release (doctoral manuscript submission, then each subsequent Zenodo report). Within a release window, no interim inferential testing is conducted that would inform a decision to continue or stop the collection.
- **Multiple comparisons:** H1, H2, and H3 are tested in sequence with no correction (primary, secondary, specificity). The four moderator analyses (6.4) are reported as exploratory and not corrected.
- **Phase separation:** data from the pre-deposit technical validation phase (Section 1.2) is excluded from every inferential analysis. It may be reported descriptively in the appendix of the doctoral manuscript only to characterise the technical readiness of the platform prior to the confirmatory phase.

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7. Data management and open science

7.1 Data collected

All data are collected through the platform inoculation.fr and stored in a secured database. Participant-level data are pseudonymised: no name, email, or directly identifying information is collected. Each participant is assigned a unique opaque identifier. The phase flag (technical_validation vs. confirmatory) is recorded at the session level.

7.2 Public release schedule

- This preregistration (v2): released at deposit (CC BY 4.0, Zenodo, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20403018).
- Anonymised dataset (CSV): released as a versioned series on Zenodo, with the first release at the date of doctoral manuscript submission and subsequent releases as the confirmatory phase continues. Each release is dated, citable, and linked to this preregistration as a related identifier.
- Analysis script: released alongside each dataset version.
- FBSS instrument and stimuli (in their final form): released with the first dataset, CC BY 4.0.

7.3 Storage and retention

Raw data are retained on the researcher's secured infrastructure for the duration of the doctoral programme plus five years, in accordance with the data-management commitments of the CEDS programme.

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8. Deviation policy

Any deviation from this preregistration that becomes necessary after the deposit date will be disclosed transparently in the doctoral manuscript and in any subsequent publication of the trial results. Deviations are categorised as follows.

- **Minor deviations** (typographical corrections, clarifications without substantive change): reported in a deviation log appendix.
- **Substantive deviations** (changes to hypotheses, primary outcome, analysis plan, or sample-size threshold): reported in the deviation log with explicit rationale and impact assessment, and accompanied by a versioned amendment to this preregistration deposited on Zenodo as a new version of DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20403018.

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9. Author and contact

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